

Evaluation of projects carried out in companies by second-year Engineering students

Marco A. C. Pereira¹, Cristiano E. R. Reis², Débora A. I. Yoshioka¹

¹School of Engineering of Lorena, University of São Paulo (USP), Brazil

² EARTH University, Costa Rica.

Email: marcopereira@usp.br, crodrigues@earth.ac.cr; debora_yoshioka@usp.br

Abstract

The realm of Engineering education has great challenges; one of them being related to taking the students to real-life situations that can simulate the future challenges of their profession. Second-year Industrial Engineering students from the Engineering School of Lorena at the University of São Paulo (Brazil) were challenged to work on projects in companies of different areas and sizes. All projects were related to improvement opportunities identified in the companies. As a quantitative outcome, the students were asked to answer questionnaires at the end of their project by the end of the semester, in which they needed to assess the development of their individual skills and to evaluate the project carried out. The qualitative methodology applied to this study, thus, evaluated through a case-study some core concepts on behalf of the students through a questionnaire. The self-assessment demonstrated a positive development of technical and transversal skills by the students that are likely to have been useful in the development phase of the project development. Students highlighted on the project side that clarity on the definition and expectation is essential, as well as previous technical knowledge relevant to the development of the activities throughout the semester. They also stressed the fact that a deep skillset on project management, coupled with quality tools and methods, are desirable, if not, essential to a fruitful pace of activities. From a summary among all the obtained data, the greatest learning for the coordination of the discipline was the importance of receiving a critical analysis from the students at the end of the project.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning; Engineering Education; Second-year Engineering students

1 Project-Based Learning: Fundamentals

The long-standing tradition of Engineering courses taught through professor-oriented classes in a passive-learning setting still figures out as the most common reality of the learning practices applied on the most colleges and universities worldwide. The passive-centered and instructor-oriented learning setting implies that the learning is unidirectional, having the student as the receiving agent of information and knowledge, while the teacher stands as the information center, acting as a message transmitter. Intensive research on education highlighted that novel learning practices can be better applied to these settings, especially taking into account that the scarcity of information availability, which was a common limiting factor to previous decades and centuries, should not be taken as a significant portion of learning centers. The widespread information available on the internet with tools that were previously unthinkable urge the necessity of revising the tradition of passive and unidirectional teaching, i.e., relying upon the need of an instructor to pass information to a student. Among the approaches developed as an adaptation to the era of information and knowledge abundance available to the learners, some active-learning and student-oriented methodologies have been disclosed and applied to numerous settings under different degrees. An example of those is Project-Based Learning (PBL), which relies as an effective tool to promote the excitement and challenge-driven learning, based on the application of actual and complex problems as the main driver for the promotion of knowledge, having the students seek the information and knowledge necessary to fulfill the solutions for such problems, and the instructor as a tutor to assist on the development of solutions.

PBL aims to place the student as the main actor in their learning process. As a result, the role of the teacher must change, since he leaves the position of bearer of all knowledge to that of facilitator of the learning process (English & Kitsantas, 2013, Mitchell & Rogers, 2020). PBL, in addition to enabling students to become responsible for their own learning, also promotes the development of transversal skills, such as: teamwork, communication and leadership, among others (Lehmann, Christensen, Du & Thrane, 2008; Chimendes,

Andrade, Rosa, Miranda & Silva, 2018; Murzi, Chowdhury, Karlovšek & Ruiz Ulloa, 2020). The use of PBL in engineering courses is a way of adding value to student learning, as well as being recognized to be effective in preparing for the professional development required in engineering-related jobs (Jollands & Molyneaux, 2012; Chimendes, Rosa, Miranda & Andrade, 2017; Larsen, Kjærsgaard, Bigum & Jacobsen, 2019).

PBL has been applied to real problems such as educational strategy in various situations of partnership between universities and companies; for example, a course on Digital Lean Manufacturing and the related industrial applications, (Raweewan & Kojima, 2020), or a group of Civil Engineering and Industrial Engineering developing solutions to problems of standardization of procedures in the Netherlands (MacLeod & van der Veen, 2020), or even in rural applications, in which Finnish students evaluated the design of innovative low-cost projects using mobile internet technologies of things in Engineering courses (Mielikäinen, Angelva & Tepsa, 2019). This is also being done in the Industrial Engineering course at the Engineering School of Lorena at the University of São Paulo. This course was first implemented in 2012 and receives 40 students annually. PBL was first implemented in the coursework in 2013, after technical visits made to schools in the United States (Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Harvard University), Portugal (University of Minho) and Brazil (University of Brasília). The lessons learned from the two North American universities was the realization of the intense partnership with companies in which their students work through projects to solve real problems (Edström & Kolmos, 2014). At the Portuguese University, one of the lessons learned was about a project-based course in which students in the fourth year of the Industrial Engineering and Management career along the same lines as American universities and with the adoption of the Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology. The University of Brasilia in its Production Engineering course also adopted PBL in specific design disciplines from the fourth to the tenth semesters of the career (Lima, Silva, Janssen, Monteiro & Souza, 2012). The Engineering School of Lorena hosts two project-based courses aimed at partnering with companies: Integrated Project of Industrial Engineering II (IPIE II) in the fourth semester and Integrated Project of Industrial Engineering III (IPIE III) in the seventh semester. The objective of IPIE II is to put the student to work on projects related to real problems that are proposed by small / medium sized companies. IPIE III has a similar objective to IPIE II, but usually with problems of greater technical complexity. This study focuses on the application of IPIE II at the Engineering School of Lorena. The case presented herein refers to a group of 39 students who took the course from August to November 2019.

2 Methodology and Application of PBL to the Study Context

The method of research utilized was case study. This research method shows inductive focus on analysis of obtained data and a descriptive one for the presentation of results. A case study is generally organized around some questions referring to "how" and "why" of such investigation, and it can be decomposed to its most relevant components. There are four essential steps for a case study. They are: (i) – delimitation of the case-unit, (ii) – data collection, (iii) – selection, analysis and data interpretation, and (iv) – report writing; the four of which are applied and can be easily visualized on the structure of this work.

The first activity of the course consisted on prospecting projects with partner companies about a month before the start of the semester. Once the partnership is closed and the project is defined, each company prepares a Project Charter with Project information. Usually, two or three meetings are held in the companies to align the project at the students' level (second year of the Engineering course) and the time they will have to carry out the project (4 months). In this class of 2019, seven projects were aligned with five companies. Table 1 presents the main characteristics of the companies and the projects carried out.

The classroom schedule during the semester had 14 meetings coordinated by the class instructor. An introductory presentation on Project Management was made in the first class, with an emphasis on six key PMBOK processes (PMI, 2017; Novaes & Andrade, 2018) Define Scope, Work Breakdown Structure, Define Activities, Sequence Activities, Estimated Activity Durations and Develop Schedule.

Table 1 – Projects developed in 2019 by the students enrolled in IPIE II

Project	Business Type	Project Goals
A	Veterinary Clinic	To improve administrative-financial and supply inventory management processes
B	ICT (Information and Communication Technology) Service Provider	To improve inventory management of ICT supplies and equipment
C	ICT Service Provider	To operate in the control of operations aiming to balance the distribution of services among the different teams working in the field.
D	Hospital	To assist in the implementation of Lean Healthcare in a sector of the Hospital
E	Steel Painting Industry	To increase the degree of use of an industrial painting line.
F	Steel Painting Industry	To develop a systematic acquisition of pallets used in the assembly of racks for the various measures of steel coils
G	Food Packaging Industry	To contribute to the improvement of the engraving process of cylinders used in rotary printers

The main phases of the project that occurred throughout the semester are presented in table 2.

Table 2 – Project Phases and Activities

Phase	Class(es)	Classroom Activity	Activity in the Business setting
1	1	Class on Project Management	None
2	2	Presentation of projects; Team formation	None
3	3 and 4	Review on theory on essential topics for the projects	First visit to the businesses
3	5 through 8	Project follow-up meetings	Business visits and meetings
4	9	Oral presentations	Project follow-up meetings
5	10 through 13	Project follow-up meetings	Business visits and meetings
6	14	Instructions on the final report, competence evaluation, and project evaluation	Business visits and meetings
7	15	None	Final oral presentation and delivery of solutions

In the second class, the teams were divided and the leader of each team was defined. In the next two classes, essential concepts for good project management were explored: PDCA, process design software and some basic quality management and productivity management tools. From the fifth to the eighth class, the instructor met with the teams on an alternating basis, i.e., a class with four teams and in the following class with the three remaining teams.

In the eighth class, the teams delivered a first project report. In the ninth class, there was a presentation of all teams to the course instructor and two guest professors. After each presentation, feedback was given by the professors. From the tenth to the thirteenth class, the instructor met again, alternately with the teams.

In the thirteenth class, the teams delivered the second partial report of the project, which was evaluated by the course instructor and returned to each team in the next class.

In the fourteenth and last face-to-face class of the course, the teams received instructions on the final presentation of the project to be made in the companies, followed by a mandatory survey with three questionnaires to assess their feedback and perception on key points.

Parallel to this schedule of activities in the classroom, between the fourth and the fourteenth week of the project, all the teams visited the companies. These visits took place at the intervals required by the project.

During the semester, the teams delivered three reports. The first was delivered in the eighth class and aimed to provide a complete description of the first phase of the project divided into four parts: problem identification, observation, analysis and action plan. The second report was delivered in the thirteenth class,

about 15 days before the final report was delivered to the company. In this report, the team should present a final draft to the report to receive feedback in order to improve the report to be delivered to the company. Finally, the third report was delivered to the company.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Evaluation of Project-Based Learning Methodology

The assessment was made from the first questionnaire called the PBL Questionnaire which contained 4 questions based on a 5-point Likert scale: 1 (Strongly disagree), 2 (partially disagree), 3 (Neither disagree - nor agree), 4 (partially agree) and 5 (Totally agree). This questionnaire was answered individually.

Table 3 presents the results for each of the four questions (column 2). From the third to the ninth columns are the simple arithmetic averages for each of the questions for the seven teams. The codes from A to G are those that represent each of the companies shown in table 1. Finally, the last column presents the simple arithmetic mean of each of the questions for the 35 respondents.

Table 3. PBL Questionnaire.

ID	Question	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	Average
1	The use of PBL in the discipline is one of the differentials of the Industrial Engineering course	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.83	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.97
2	I understand that PBL concepts should be used in more subjects of the course	4.50	4.60	5.00	4.67	4.80	5.00	5.00	4.77
3	PBL methodology makes learning more motivating	4.17	5.00	5.00	4.50	4.75	5.00	5.00	4.74
4	The PBL methodology improves the development of interpersonal relationships	4.33	4.80	4.50	4.83	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.77

The data in table 3 show almost complete agreement that the use of PBL in this course is one of the differentials of the Industrial Engineering coursework from the students' perspective. The other three questions show that students have a very high degree of agreement that the concepts of PBL should be used in other disciplines, that the use of methodology makes learning more motivating and improves the development of interpersonal relationships. All of these results reveal that the PBL methodology is recognized and validated by students as very important in their professional training.

3.2 Competences

The assessment was made using a questionnaire called the Competence Questionnaire, which contained 10 questions based on the Likert scale in the same way as the PBL Questionnaire. This questionnaire was answered individually. It aimed to evaluate the development of 2 transversal competences (teamwork, personal development) and 1 technical competence (project management).

Table 4 presents the results for each of the ten questions and its structure of columns and numerical results is identical to that of the PBL Questionnaire. The first four questions refer to teamwork. Questions 5 and 6 refer to two aspects of personal development (creativity and critical thinking). Finally, questions 7-10 were related to the technical competence of project management.

The analysis of the first four questions related to teamwork reveals that the students more agreed than disagreed, since all answers are higher than the average 3.0. However, a point to highlight is that, in general, students knew how to manage conflicts well in all teams (question 4), which suggests a good degree of maturity taking into account that they are second year engineering students and aged average of 19 years. On the other hand, the results of questions 1 to 3 point out serious difficulties in relation to teamwork for the team that worked on project A (Veterinary Clinic) and a little difficulty for the team that worked on project C (ICT service provider).

Table 4. Competence Questionnaire

ID	Question	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	Average
1	All the members of my team contributed to the success of the work	2.67	5.00	2.50	4.00	3.60	4.80	5.00	3.88
2	The success of my team was due to the union between its members	2.67	5.00	4.00	4.33	3.40	5.00	5.00	4.12
3	All the members of my team fulfilled the tasks established	2.67	4.60	3.25	4.33	3.60	5.00	5.00	4.03
4	All conflicts experienced in my team were overcome in a coherent and respectful way	4.83	5.00	3.75	4.83	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.63
5	The project helped develop my creativity for problem solving	4.17	5.00	4.75	4.17	3.80	5.00	5.00	4.51
6	I realize that I developed a greater critical sense in this project that helps me to evaluate the differences in work proposals	3.83	5.00	4.75	4.17	4.40	4.40	4.75	4.43
7	The meetings that took place were productive and decisive for the good results of the project	3.33	4.60	4.50	4.00	2.80	4.80	5.00	4.09
8	My team met all deadlines	4.83	4.80	5.00	4.83	3.40	4.40	5.00	4.31
9	My team knew how to manage time well, fulfilling the proposed schedule	2.67	4.40	4.75	4.33	2.20	4.60	5.00	3.91
10	The necessary knowledge for the development of the project was sought from different sources	4.83	5.00	4.25	4.00	3.40	4.80	5.00	4.46

Regarding the two questions that aimed to evaluate aspects of personal development, it appears that students in general more agreed than disagreed that the project helped in the development of creativity and critical sense.

One aspect that draws attention in the analysis of the results of transversal skills is that when it comes to individual development (creativity and critical sense) the numerical results suggest their development in greater intensity, from the perspective of the respondents, when compared to the characteristics of teamwork who do not depend only on an action by the individual (student), but on the other individuals (colleagues) who interact with him in the team.

Questions 7 to 10 are related to the technical competence of project management. In the four questions, the students more agreed than disagreed in relation to aspects of the development of a project, which points out that these aspects (productive meetings, meeting deadlines and time management) were developed during the execution of the project. The question 10 stands out, which is related to a typical characteristic of PBL, which is the fact that students often need to acquire specific technical knowledge throughout the project. And the results reveal that students sought knowledge from different sources, since not all the technical information they could have only with the course instructor.

3.3 Course evaluation

The third questionnaire called the Discipline Evaluation Questionnaire aimed at evaluating the discipline and contained four open questions, which consisted in essay-like questions answered by the team after a meeting between its members in the fourteenth week.

The first question was: What are the positive aspects of the project carried out? The answers given presented a series of positive points involving technical and transversal skills, as well as aspects of professional life. Four teams stressed the importance of having carried out a project through an experience in the practice of solving a real problem. Three teams highlighted the issue of professional responsibility that this project brought to the students, because for all its members it was the first time that they were facing a medium or high complexity

challenge in a company. The learnings were highlighted, which were accelerated from technical topics that came into contact for the first time, such as ERP (management software), logistics and specific Lean Manufacturing tools (Value Stream Mapping, Chronoanalysis). Some teams pointed out that the projects made it possible to experience teamwork in practice, as well as “professional” communication with managers and employees with whom they had contact.

The second question was: What are the points that need to be improved in the discipline of IPIE II? Three teams pointed out the need to improve the project contracting process before the beginning of the semester: “further study of the feasibility of the proposed problem” (Project F - Steel Painting Industry); “To establish more precisely the problem to be studied, as it turned out to be greater than that contained in the Project charter” (Project A - Veterinary Clinic); “Greater clarity in the definition of the project’s focus by the company” (Project B - ICT service provider). Some other points were also pointed out so that they can be improved: a more in-depth feedback from the teacher for the reports delivered, and the availability of a technical bibliography to support projects of greater complexity.

The third question was: What previous knowledge is very important to develop the project in the discipline of IPIE II? The responses were very varied, but pointed to a series of technical knowledge that students had already acquired in the first three semesters of their course, such as: (i) - quality management tools (Ishikawa diagram, 5 whys); (ii) - productivity management tools (5w2h, Kanban, Kaizen, Key Process Indicator) and (iii) - management tools in general (SWOT, flowcharts).

The fourth question was: Would the team indicate the company in which it worked so that new projects in the discipline are carried out there? Yes or no? Why? Four of the teams replied that YES (Project B - ICT Service Provider; Project D - Hospital; Project F - Steel Painting Industry; Project G - Food Packaging Industry). And all the answers were assertive and highlighted the intense learning that the team had. Three of the teams answered NO (Project A - Veterinary Clinic; Project C - ICT Service Provider; Project E - Steel Paint Industry). Each of the teams when answering NO pointed out reasons for their answer, two of which stood out: difficulties in communicating with managers and / or employees of the company and difficulties in receiving information from the company necessary to carry out the project.

Two projects were carried out at the ICT service provider. Below, the answer given by the two teams:

YES, because everyone we interact with in the company was very open during the execution of the project (Project B)

NO, since the group’s performance was limited due to technical information that the company cannot provide. However, the team emphasizes that the company is extremely receptive and provided us with great support. So, if the project was in another area of the company it could be very interesting (Project C)

This response from the team that worked on project C shows that the problem was not related to the company, but with characteristics of the project that contained technical information that the company cannot provide due to confidentiality issues with its supplier. In this case, it is clear that the answer was NO, but with a possibility that it could be YES if it were in another area of the company.

Two projects were also carried out in the steel painting industry. A similar fact to the one described above also occurred, as one of the teams signaled positively and the other negatively. The responses were:

YES, because the company shows confidence in the students’ work, and gave the group a lot of freedom of action and welcomed us in a very solicitous way. (Project F)

NO, because the company unfortunately has a series of communication problems, which impacted the quality of delivery reliability. (Project E).

Reading these two responses reveals quite different scenarios in the same company. In reality, students when answering the question did not directly analyze the company, but the employees of the company with whom they had contact. This is a very complex factor to be evaluated by the instructor when defining the project before the semester begins, as the evaluation of the project is technical, and it is difficult to assess the degree of communication that company employees will have with students.

The only categorical NO was the students who carried out the project at the veterinary clinic. This seems to be related to the fact that it is a small company with high management informality and a low degree of standardization of its processes.

The Competencies Questionnaire analyzed in section 5.2 allows for another type of analysis: the arithmetic mean of the respondents of the teams for each of the three competencies. Table 5 shows these results and the last line shows the average of the answers to the 10 questions for all respondents in each of the teams. This was not the objective of this questionnaire, but the results allow a more in-depth analysis of the answers given to the fourth question of the Discipline Evaluation Questionnaire.

Table 5. Team Evaluation

Competence	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Teamwork	2.96	4.89	3.38	4.38	3.90	4.95	5.00
Personal Development	4.00	5.00	4.75	4.17	4.10	4.70	4.88
Project Management	3.50	4.70	4.63	4.29	2.95	4.65	5.00
Average	3.38	4.84	4.15	4.30	3.56	4.78	4.97

A point that draws attention is the fact that the four teams that answered that they would indicate the company to carry out a new project are the ones that have the highest arithmetic mean of the answers in this competency questionnaire. And the three teams that answered that they would not indicate for the new project are those that have the lowest arithmetic mean in relation to the development of competencies. Was the students' perception about the development of skills linked to the good performance of the project? This is a thought-provoking question, to which the first answer is apparently yes, but only better research could better clarify this point.

Two facts stand out, the almost unanimous answers of total agreement of all the elements of the team that worked in the project G (Food Packaging Industry). This team, when indicating the company so that new projects could be carried out, replied: "Yes, because everyone involved in the project was very helpful and available for any doubts and problems that arose". This answer seems to reinforce that the students' perception of skills development is related to the success of the project, including the good interaction between students and employees of the partner company.

On the other hand, it is also worth noting the fact that the only categorical NO (Project A - Veterinary Clinic) was given to the team that apparently had problems with teamwork, as shown by the average 2.96 in table 5. Therefore, this categorical NO may be related to problems that go beyond the informal management of the company. This too is an assumption that would need to be further investigated.

The analysis of the teams' responses in the open questionnaire when confronted with the arithmetic averages in this table 5 point out ways for further research to be carried out. The application of evaluation questionnaires is relevant to the management of a discipline of projects carried out in companies, which are quite different from traditional and contentious disciplines. The greatest learning for the coordination of the discipline is about the importance of receiving a critical analysis from the students at the end of the project.

4 Conclusion

The development and application of alternative methods of learning in Engineering is a continuous effort to fulfil the expectations of a trained engineer to the challenges one will face outside of the Academic settings. Project-Based Learning, as an example of the possible array of new methodologies applied to Engineering courses, has been established as an adequate method to integrate theoretical core concepts of Industrial Engineering to open-ended problems faced by actual businesses through the approach taken by the Engineering School of Lorena at the University of São Paulo. The findings described herein demonstrate the development of competences throughout the application of PBL with second-year Industrial Engineering students, relying on the development and validation of solutions to projects proposed by partner industries.

The results demonstrate that, albeit a wide variance of degree of satisfaction of working with a type and size of business, positive outcomes were obtained. Using Likert-analysis, the results demonstrate accordance to the positive outcomes self-evaluated by the students regarding the methodology applied to the course, as well as to the development of core competences by themselves, and aspects of teamwork. In this sense, this work summarizes that, through proper guidance, the application of PBL can be a rather powerful tool to bring the students close to the realities they will likely face in a few years after graduation within Engineering settings.

5 References

- Chimendes, V. C. G.; Andrade, H. S.; Rosa, A. C. M.; Miranda, Y. C. C. R. & Silva, M. B. (2018). Práticas pedagógicas para desenvolver o espírito crítico científico no aluno. *Espacios* (Caracas). 39 (49), 10-20.
- Chimendes, V. C. G., Rosa, A. C. M.; Miranda, Y. C. C. R. & Andrade, H. S. (2017). The use of Multidisciplinary, Interdisciplinarity and Transdisciplinarity to develop the Critical and Scientific Spirit in the student. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science*, 4, 1-6.
- Edström, K., & Kolmos, A. (2014). PBL and CDIO: Complementary Models for Engineering Education Development. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 39(5), 539-555.
- English, M. C., & Kitsantas, A. (2013). Supporting Student Self-Regulated Learning in Problem- and Project-Based Learning. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning*, 7(2). 128-150.
- Jollands, M., & Molyneaux, T. (2012). Project-based learning as a contributing factor to graduates work readiness. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 37(2), 143-154.
- Larsen, S. B., Kjærsgaard, N. C., Bigum, P. V., & Jacobsen, P. (2019) Understanding how students learn in project-based courses: A review of literature. *Proceedings of SEFI 47th Annual Conference*. Budapest, Hungary. 1684-1693.
- Lehmann, M.; Christensen, P.; Du, M. & Thrane, M. (2008) Problem-oriented and project-based learning (POPBL) as an innovative learning strategy for sustainable development in engineering education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 283-295. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/03043790802088566>
- Lima, R. M., Silva, J. M., Janssen, N., Monteiro, S. B., & Souza, J. C. F. (2012). Project-based learning course design: a service design approach. *International Journal of Services and Operations Management*, 11(3), 293-313.
- MacLeod, M. & van der Veen, J. T. (2020) Scaffolding interdisciplinary project-based learning: a case study, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 45:3, 363-377. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2019.1646210>
- Mielikäinen, M. T., Juhani Angelva, J. & Tepsa, T. (2019) From customer projects to ECTS. *Proceedings of SEFI 47th Annual Conference*. Budapest, Hungary. 780-786.
- Mitchell, J. E. & Rogers, I. (2020) Staff perceptions of implementing project-based learning in engineering education, *European Journal of Engineering Education*. 45(3) 349-362. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2019.1641471>
- Murzi, H. G., Chowdhury, T. M., Karlovšek, J. & Ruiz Ulloa, B. C. (2020). Working in large teams: Measuring the impact of a teamwork model to facilitate teamwork development in engineering students working in a real project. *International Journal of Engineering Education* 36(1), 274-295
- Novaes, F. A. M. & Andrade, H. S. (2018). Um ensaio sobre o direcionamento para a criação de projetos relacionados à políticas públicas. *Espacios* (Caracas), v. 39(11), 1-12.
- Project Management Institute – PMI (2017). A guide to the project management body of knowledge: PMBOK guide, PMI, 6th ed.
- Rawewan, M. & Kojima, F. (2020) Digital lean manufacturing - Collaborative university-industry education in systems design for lean transformation. *Procedia Manufacturing*. 45. 183-188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2020.04.092>